

Determination of Thallium at Ppm Levels in Rocks and Minerals by Flame Atomic Absorption Spectrometry

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A solvent extraction atomic absorption spectrometry (AAS) method for the determination of thallium at parts per million levels in rocks and minerals have been described. The method involves sample decomposition by heating with mixture of hydrofluoric-perchloric acid, followed by extraction of thallium as iodo-complex with TOPO-MIBK from dilute hydrochloric acid medium. Flame AAS measurements for thallium is made from the organic phase. The method has been applied to the determination of thallium in a number of granite rocks and manganese ore samples. Precision studies by replicate analysis of one sample (granite B-26) gave an RSD of 6.6%.

THE extremely low level of thallium in rocks and minerals makes its determination a difficult problem. Several spectrophotometric^{1,2} and fluorimetric^{3,4} methods are available but these are too cumbersome and time consuming to be used in routine analysis. Atomic absorption spectrometry (AAS) offers distinct advantage over the other methods, but its sensitivity is not sufficient enough to permit measurements for thallium directly from the sample solution⁵. Pre-concentration is, therefore, necessary and this will not only increase the analytical sensitivity but also overcome the interference from matrix elements. Hannaker and Hughee⁶ employed n-butyl acetate extraction of thallium from silicate rocks and its flame atomic absorption measurements from the organic phase. The method needs multiple extractions and washings to effect selectivity in extraction. Donaldson and Wang⁷ proposed an iodide extraction method where thallium has to be back-extracted into the aqueous phase for AAS measurements. Thus both the methods have inherent disadvantages. In this paper we have described an iodide extraction procedure for AAS determination of thallium which is practically free from the above limitations and permits determination of parts per million levels of thallium in rocks and minerals with good precision and accuracy.

Experimental

A Varian AA-6 atomic absorption instrument fitted with a Varian hollow cathode lamp was used for the AAS measurements. Measurements have been made at 278.6 nm using air-acetylene flame and standard operating conditions.

Standard thallium solution ($1000 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) was prepared by dissolving thallium oxide (specpure) in dilute HCl. Further dilutions were made as necessary. TOPO-MIBK reagent was prepared by dissolving tri-n-octyl phosphine oxide (2 g) in methyl

isobutyl ketone (100 ml). All chemicals used were of A.R. grade.

Sample decomposition and preparation of test solution: Powdered sample (1 g) was treated with perchloric acid (5 ml) and hydrofluoric acid (15 ml). The mixture was slowly heated to dryness on a hot-plate. The dried mass was treated with perchloric acid (5 ml), heated to dryness, the mass dissolved in dilute HCl (30 ml; 2 N).

Liquid-liquid extraction and AAS measurements: The above test solution was diluted to a volume of 50 ml with 2N HCl. Ascorbic acid (1 g) and potassium iodide (1 g) were added to it and the mixture was shaken with TOPO-MIBK reagents (5 ml) for 1 min and allowed to settle. The organic phase mixed with anhydrous sodium sulphate (1 g) and the supernate was used for AAS measurements.

Calibration solutions containing 1–10 μg of thallium were taken and each solution was diluted with 2N HCl (50 ml), mixed with ascorbic acid (1 g) and potassium iodide (1 g) and extracted with TOPO-MIBK (5 ml). The organic phase after drying over anhydrous sodium sulphate was used for calibration.

Results and Discussion

Several iodide forming elements, viz. Sb, Bi, In, Cd, Cu and Pb are extracted along with thallium under the experimental conditions, but they do not cause any interference. In case of sulphide ores, where appreciable amounts (0.1%) of copper or lead is present it is desirable to remove these elements before carrying out extraction of thallium. Copper can be removed as the soluble copper-ammine complex by treatment with excess of ammonia wherein thallium is retained in the hydrous oxide precipitate. Removal of lead is effected by precipitating it as lead sulphate with dilute sulphuric acid⁸.

The proposed method has been applied to the determination of thallium in a number of granite rock and manganese ore samples (Table 1). The results are quite comparable to the reported⁶ method. Four standard reference samples have also been analysed for thallium by this method and the results compare favourably with the reported values. Precision of the method obtained by replicate analysis of granite sample B-26, showed RSD-6.6%.

The proposed method is simple and rapid because the extraction is very clean and complete in single stage. This can be applied to the determination of thallium as low as 0.2 ppm in diverse types of geological materials.

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TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF THALLIUM IN ROCKS AND MINERALS

Description	Found	Tl (ppm) Recommended	Other method ^d
Manganese ore from Keonjhar area, Orissa			
No 1	1.6	—	1.5
No 2	1.2	—	1.3
No 3	1.4	—	1.3
No 4	2.5	—	2.6
Manganese ore from Sandur area			
No 1	1.3	—	1.2
No. 2	2.7	—	2.7
Granite rock, B-26	0.8	—	0.9
BCR-1 (USGS)	0.35	0.3 ^a	0.35
AGV-1 (USGS)	1.20	1.0 ^a	1.1
GSP-1 (USGS)	1.0	1.1 ^b	1.0
ACE (CRPG, France)	0.95	0.9 ^c	0.85
Analytical results available from ^a Ref 6, ^b Ref 9, ^c Ref 10 ^d According to Hannaka and Hughee method ⁶			

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